

FACTORS CAUSING GENDER DISCRIMINATION AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, information about gender equality, that is, information about the work of education and campaigns on gender equality, is highlighted. Also, recommendations on the factors causing gender discrimination and their solutions are presented.

Key word: Gender justice, feminist movement, gender stereotypes, gender discrimination, gender approach.

Introduction:

Today, special attention is paid to gender equality in our society. Opinions such as equal rights of men and women, freedom of whatever gender they are are put forward.

Gender equality and sexual equality, more precisely: equality between men and women, is a concept that implies the achievement of equal rights between men and women in the family and society and other legal relations. According to some researchers, gender equality is the next stage of socio-sexual relations after the patriarchal system. The principle of gender equality is to study and eliminate all social barriers that prevent the emergence of a person as a person, as well as to create equal social opportunities for realizing the personality of men and women in all spheres of life.

Work is being carried out on the systematization of gender equality, laws protecting the legal interests of "women" and "men" have been developed, as well as measures to combat gender discrimination are being carried out. However, it is not an exaggeration to say that stereotypes against women in some regions and communities, as well as the existence of values that are now considered a vice, are one of the most pressing issues.

Factors causing gender discrimination:

- Fixed stereotypes about women and men;
- Some stereotypes are considered values;
- Gender segregation in the profession and salary distribution;

In social psychology, the term stereotype is defined as an overgeneralized belief about a certain category of people. Stereotypes encourage prejudice and can occur for a number of reasons.

Stereotypes start in the family. Improper restrictions imposed by parents on children in the family. For example: A boy can only play with technical toys, and a girl is told: "Boys play with this, "You play yours" - dolls or various cooking and medical equipment are brought by parents with restrictions, ignoring their interests. Such situations are the starting point of stereotypes. MFY is required to further increase the promotion of gender equality by organizing seminars for parents and educating them when necessary.

Mental views such as women are emotional and men are tough are also a form of stereotypes. Also, in the family, a girl child should be someone's wife, do housework and raise children, and a man should be the head of the house and the breadwinner. In order to ensure gender equality, first of all, it is necessary to create such an environment in the family, which is considered the smallest link of society. It is appropriate to train young people in this regard in educational institutions, organize seminars and exhibitions, and attract specialists. In addition, gender discrimination is also caused by the assignment of labor subjects to boys and girls separately in general secondary educational institutions. As a result, professional stereotypes are embedded in the minds of young people. In order to put an end to this, it is necessary to include the topics of gender equality in the textbooks and revise the teaching methods.

German psychologist, sociologist, one of the founders of neo-Freudianism, representative of humanistic psychoanalysis Erich Seligmann Fromm (Erich Seligmann Fromm) in his work entitled "Male and Female" came to the following conclusions while analyzing the nature and characteristics of representatives of the two sexes and the problem of gender equality: "Equality means identity. The demand for equality is polar in nature: no one should use the other as a means to an end, despite all their differences, because each person is an end unto himself. And this means that every person should have the freedom to develop his individual characteristics and uniqueness as a representative of his species and nation. Equality does not imply the denial of differences, but the possibility of their full realization.

A significant gap between men and women remains in the labor market. Sexual violence and exploitation, the unequal distribution of unpaid care and housework, and the fact that elements of discrimination still remain in some decision-making remain major obstacles to development. In order to overcome such urgent problems, we need to strengthen feminist movements, and if we promote such movements at every level of our society, it will show its results.

What is the feminist movement? Feminist movements work for women's rights, including the right to vote, to hold public office, to work, to receive fair wages and to close the gender pay gap, to own property, to get an education, to have equal rights in marriage, and to have maternity leave.

Proverbs used contrary to gender equality in folklore:

- The angel of a woman is the angel of life;
- The sitting girl finds her place;
- He who has a son has a role;
- A girl's appearance is pleasant;
- Take the farmer's cow, the widow's daughter;
- Men are destroyed by women and earth;
- Men build the house, women build the hearth;

It is necessary to make changes to the ingrained proverbs affecting the spirituality of such a society. For example:

A woman's angel-knowledgeable, blonde;

- An educated girl will find her place;
- In the girl's vision;
- Those who have knowledge have their place;

In conclusion, gender equality is one of the urgent problems of today, and we need to pay more attention to it. In this regard, we need to carry out propaganda work in every part of our society, starting from the proverbs that are ingrained in our spirituality. At the same time, we can achieve the expected result by strengthening feminist movements and eliminating certain stereotypes. Strengthening propaganda work in organizations and educational institutions, making changes and ensuring the legal interests of every citizen of the society respecting his personality will be a foundation not only for the development of our country, but also for a strong social life.

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